

Intelligence Surveillance Reconnaissance “Search Window”

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Abstract - This report was commissioned by Lockheed Martin Corporation in order to develop a predictive model capable of identifying potential enemy ballistic missile launch sites prior to launch. This model will use geospatial data in conjunction with intelligence, surveillance, and reconnaissance assets in order to identify likely missile launch sites. The utilization of this model will save time when planning missions and engaging targets. This model will provide the commander with the ability destroy a launch site before it has a chance to fire a missile. Since enemy offensive missiles heavily outnumber the amount of American defensive missiles, this model uses an offensive approach in a field that has historically taken a defensive stance. Destroying enemy launch sites before they can fire ensures the most efficient use of missile assets. The prototype algorithm will be built using a commercial geospatial software tool, ArcGIS, and evaluating open-source data. The prototype will evaluate geographical data in order to focus assets on areas that are conducive to missile launch sites. This algorithm will then be exported to a tactical operating system capable of simulating missile engagements on a global scale and allowing commanders to make informed decisions regarding missile threats. The result of this project will have two parts. The first part will be a model in ArcGIS that will identify potential enemy launch sites based on geographic location and characteristics of the terrain. The second part of this project will be a graphical display that will output all relevant information to the commander. This information will include the coordinates of the possible launch sites, expected missile type, and range of each weapon system.

INTRODUCTION

Air and Missile Defense is an increasingly important part of our nation's national security due to the proliferation of missile threats by foreign powers. The current approach to Air and Missile Defense relies on intercepting incoming threats post launch. This approach is cost, labor, and resource intensive, and it will inevitably fail because there are simply more enemy offensive missiles than friendly defensive missiles. Although the United States has the world's largest military, the U.S. does not have as many defensively postured missiles as foreign powers have offensively postured missiles. This “one-to-one” or “multi-to-one” approach is ineffective because of two issues: (1) “missile intercept inaccuracy” and (2) “resource

management insufficiency” [1]. Missile intercept inaccuracy is an issue because the USA’s missiles are still unable to intercept an incoming threat with 100% accuracy. Resource management insufficiency refers to the fact that if an enemy power fired all of their missiles, the USA does not have the resources needed to engage each one. These issues persist because they require the immense allocation of resources and funds from the military force. In addition, the engagement of multiple airborne projectiles is time intensive and takes decision makers away from other aspects of a battle. Another benefit is that the destruction of a launch site before a projectile is in the air prevents the need to account for falling debris from an intercepted missile. This shift in missile defense strategy also caters to the future needs of the country. In Bill Gertz’s recent article for Fox News, he discussed the up and coming Chinese missile technology. These new missiles travel at hypersonic speeds and are capable of bypassing American surface to air defensive missiles [2].

The conflicts of today have an increased reliance on missile assets, as evidenced in the ongoing conflict with Syria and the constant threat of Iran. Under the current missile defense strategy, the United States must increase the size of its missile arsenal as other countries do the same. As previously stated, the current method for missile defense has changed in response to the sheer size in numbers of foreign missile threats. Therefore, the desired end state of this project is to provide the capability to identify launch sites before a launch occurs. This process of “killing the archer before he can shoot an arrow” will be less time, cost, and resource intensive and will lead to a more efficient use of missile assets. The prototype algorithm will give decision makers a better understanding of the battlefield and the ability to make well-informed decisions based on the most likely locations for enemy launch sites.

FRAMING THE PROBLEM

Defining the Problem

Due to the technical nature of this problem and the amount of task specific information needed, the background information and necessary functionality for the algorithm were gathered from Subject Matter Expert (SME) input and stakeholder preference. The SME input came from LMC personnel, USMA staff with an air defense background and from the 32nd Army Air and Missile Defense Command (32nd AAMDC). The input from these sources was critical through all phases of the project in terms of defining the

problem and generating solutions. The discussion with the SMEs led to the generation of the following problem statement:

Improve the model developed in AY13, providing commanders with a tool that predicts enemy missile launch sites. The results will be integrated with the tactical common operating picture so that the target can be quickly serviced. Improvements will include an easier to use and more automated system.

The use of this algorithm will allow decision makers to identify enemy threat areas and improve the use of missile defense and intelligence assets in a given area of operation. The areas of interest identified by the model will be classified based on their overall threat level. Analyzing an area based on its perceived threat level, the decision makers have the ability to prioritize the placement of ISR assets in the most useful manner.

Assumptions

In conjunction with the development of the problem statement and definition of the problem, the following assumptions were made in order to focus the scope of the study:

- The “basing” of hostile mobile missile threats and the transportation vehicles moving enemy missile assets are assumed to share performance metrics (maximum speed, degree of tilt, fuel capacity, et cetera) with the MIM4 Patriot Missile System and Heavy Equipment Transport (HET) trucks
- When evaluating the “threat set” for a given country, the assets available to the country are constant across all regions of the selected country
- There is geographical data available for the selected country (slope, vegetation, water sources, et cetera)
- Fuel type is a limiting factor for launch points. Liquid fuel rockets are launched from larger areas while solid fuel rockets are less restricted

METHODOLOGY

The project team followed the Systems Decisions Process (SDP) throughout in order to best define the problem, generate solutions, make decisions, and to implement solutions. The SDP consists of four phases, each containing several sub-phases [3]. The following sections outline each phase and sub-phases are identified and defined. This project deviated from the SDP at certain points in order to fit the needs of the project. The follow-on sections of the report explain how each phase of the SDP was used in the project. The full SDP can be seen in the figure below.

FIGURE 1
SYSTEMS DECISION PROCESS [3]

Problem Definition

Problem definition is the most important step of the Systems Decision Process. This phase of the SDP provides a foundation and direction for the entire project. The first step of the problem definition phase is to create a problem statement that will be addressed by the completion of the project. The problem statement for this project is to improve the model developed in AY13, specifically; to create a tool that predicts likely enemy missile launch and cache sites. In the end, the tools result will be combined with a common tactical operating picture that can quickly survey the intelligence. Improvements will include an easier to use and more automated system. The main components of the problem definition phase addressed are:

- **Research & Stakeholder Analysis:** This component of the problem definition phase defines the functions, objectives, and constraints of the project. At the project launch meeting, LMC provided the team with their overall expectations of the project and its role in being integrated into their missile defense simulator. Stakeholder analysis was an ongoing process for this project in order to maintain the scope that the LMC team envisioned. When LMC’s expectations had been established, the team interviewed a variety of subject matter experts for two reasons: to begin the brainstorming process and understanding the capability gaps of missile defense today and to make sure that the expectations of LMC were plausible and realistic. The findings provided the team with background knowledge of missile defense and led to more questions being asked. Additionally, the findings caused a narrower focus on the parameters. The conclusions identified current capability gaps in missile defense and guided the

set of parameters used in ArcGIS. The recommendations identified the most important factors of the project and further identified the necessary capabilities for the model [3].

- **Functional Analysis:** This component of the problem definition phase seeks to identify the desired functionality of the project. This phase also identifies the interactions of these functions and their integration into the overall system [3]. This information was primarily used to determine how the algorithm within the ArcGIS model should operate. Similar to stakeholder analysis, the primary source of information for this component was interviews with SMEs.

Solution Design

The second phase of the SDP involves the three sub-phases that lead to the generation of strategies to solve the problem. For this project, there were three phases of solution design. The first two were dedicated to finding a way to solve the problem, and the third was dedicated to validating the model. The three sub-phases of the solution design phase are:

- **Idea Generation:** This sub-phase is dedicated to finding possible ways that the problem could be solved. This phase does not need to find the final solution, but potential solutions that could solve the problem. Techniques for this stage could include brainstorming, morphology, group-think, and devil's advocate [1].
- **Alternative Generation and Implementation:** This sub-phase evaluates the list of potential solutions from the first sub-phase and measures their value and feasibility. The decision of which solution to implement is based on the cost and benefit relationship of each candidate solution.
- **Solution Evaluation:** The third and final sub-phase of Solution Design is solution evaluation. Evaluating this project's solution was essential because of the real-world applications that it encompasses. Creating a working algorithm that cannot be used by an operator is not useful. As a result, the Army's Air Defense Community validated the model's output to see if the areas identified by the model were similar to those identified by Air Defense experts.

Decision Making

The decision making phase of a project involves the careful evaluation and improvement of the various candidate solutions; in this case the ISR search window model. The decision makers participate in interim reviews and final decision presentations. Based on these interactions, the decision maker will select the solution to implement. Decision makers review the candidate solution value, cost, sensitivity analysis, and risk analysis. They also decide if more improvements are needed and make the difficult value versus cost tradeoff decision among the efficient solutions. Will the benefits of the ISR search window model be worth

the investment it would take to implement it? In order to make this decision, the decision maker will review the three tasks involved with decision-making. These include value scoring/costing, sensitivity/risk analysis, and improvement/trade-off analysis.

- **Value Scoring and Costing:** This first of three sub-phases involves taking each candidate solution and comparing it relative to each value measure in an attempt to determine which solution is best. Operations, testing, modeling, simulation, and expert opinion are all methods by which the SDP draws from in order to conduct solution scoring. This phase also includes scoring data submitted and validated by the Army's Air Defense Community.
- **Sensitivity and Risk Analysis:** The goal of this sub-phase is to examine if the preferred solution determined by solution scoring changes given that there are changes in the assumptions or the value measures of that particular candidate solution. This process is completed by varying the swing weights given changes in values measures to analyze the strength of the model as well as examine uncertainty [3]. It is important to understand the most sensitive assumptions or parameters and to assess the key risks.
- **Improvements and Tradeoff Analysis:** This phase is an opportunity to improve the solution. Tradeoffs must be made between efficient solutions. With input from experts and stakeholders, the model will be improved before the final decision is made. With these improvements, it is important to analyze the cost and benefits for every change the model undergoes, in order to select the best improvement.

Solution Implementation

The Solution Implementation phase is the final phase of the SDP and is arguably the most difficult to accomplish. This phase focuses on turning client's expectations for the system into reality [3]. This phase has three sub phases: planning, executing, and monitoring & controlling. This phase is where all of the planning and analysis become reality. Although it is the final phase of the SDP, it is possible to return to other phases of the SDP depending on changing circumstances such as evolving customer needs, environmental changes, or other changing factors.

PROBLEM DEFINITION

Stakeholder Analysis

Stakeholder analysis was a vital step in this investigation for several reasons. First, constant communication with decision-makers ensured that the final product was useful to LMC and the Army. Gathering information on both the capabilities and capability-gaps of current systems helped shape the scope of the project. The primary sources of stakeholder analysis consisted of interviews with LMC and 32nd Army Air and Missile Defense Command (32nd

AAMDC). LMC provided their needs, wants, and desires for the model and how it would ideally fit into their missile defense test bed. 32nd AAMDC mainly explained the current state of air defense and how our approach could improve missile defense. This communication allowed the group to identify the needs, wants, and desires of the stakeholders. Not all wants and desires were accomplished in the project, but the list is included below.

- **Needs:** Take a more effective planning approach by identifying missile launch sites prior to launch. Generate an output that can be used by battlefield commanders to make informed decisions (Graphical User Interface)
- **Wants:** Apply a different threat set and terrain analysis for different countries. Create a choropleth map capable of showing locations that most likely contain launch sites
- **Desires:** Incorporate weather, traffic, and social media data into the model. Identify potential maritime launch sites

As a result of the needs, wants, and desires of the model, the following findings, conclusions, and recommendations came about to focus the scope of the model.

- **Findings:** According to the Congressional Research Service of "Iran's Ballistic Missile and Space Launch Programs," Missile Systems operate optimally from 66%-100% of their maximum effective range. Different countries have different arsenal of missiles with varying capabilities and payloads. During an international missile engagement, weather does not restrict missile launches. According to analysts at the IHS Jane's Military and Security Assessments Intelligence Centre, missiles can use liquid or solid fuel. Terrain is most likely factor to render a launch site infeasible
- **Conclusions:** Missile systems will be different distances away from their target depending on its fuel type (solid missiles travel farther than liquid)
- **Recommendations:** Gather intelligence reports of liquid and solid propellants to determine the range to narrow potential launch sites area. Create different "range rings" for different defended assets and hostile bases.

The information and guidance received from the stakeholders provided a direction for research and in the overall design of the model. The internal and external sources of information gave the project team the information needed to build and design the algorithm.

Functional Analysis

Functional Analysis is a systematic process to identify the system functions and interfaces required to achieve the system objectives. The fundamental objective of this study

encompasses the prediction of hostile missile launch and storage sites in order to reduce search sectors and focus friendly ISR assets. Figure 2 below is a functional hierarchy of the search window, identifying the main points of the system.

FIGURE 2
FUNCTIONAL HIERARCHY OF SEARCH WINDOW

The first step to be taken when using the model is to input the given data on the current threat set. This allows the model to specify which areas are most likely to contain launch sites. These inputs include:

- **Selected Country-** Determines the area of interest in order to bring up the map in ArcGIS
- **Defended Assets-** Enter the grid coordinates of the known Forward Operation Bases, Combat Outposts, or any known location of friendly assets. This will help identify who is in the most danger and help identify potential launch sites
- **Friendly Offensive Locations-** Enter the grid coordinates of any known locations of friendly launch sites, if we were to use land offensives
- **Threat Set-** Enter the known missile type(s) of the enemy to help identify the size. This will help narrow possible location launch sites by determining what areas would be feasible to transport the different size missiles. In addition, identifying the payload (if known) helps specify what areas would be in danger once location sites are identified.
- **Fuel Type-** Enter either liquid or solid fuel type, which will determine the range of the missile
- **Any Additional Available Intel-** This includes any known grid coordinates of enemy locations, or the coordinates for any underground silos or installation sites.

Once the user identifies this data in ArcGIS, it will produce a map display of the area of interest. A visual of what this looks like is shown below in Figure 3:

FIGURE 3
AREA OF INTEREST MAP

This area of interest is the area of the selected country where the potential launch site is located. Following this step, the parameters for the specific country identified will be used in the model. These parameters can be found in databases controlled by the Army Geospatial Center. These parameters can include land cover, vegetation, slope, roads, turn radius of the vehicle carrying the missile, military compounds in the area, traffic, weather and defended assets. Parameters will differ amongst different countries because each has different standard operating procedures on the way they conduct the different kinds of operations. ArcGIS will then look at the given parameters and filter the given terrain in order to identify potential launch sites. Below are outputs of some of these parameters in ArcGIS. Figure 4 identifies slope where red indicates the steepest slope, or unsuitable for a missile launch, while green would be the most suitable.

FIGURE 4
SLOPE MAP

Figure 5 identifies the roads and land cover. Dark green represents forested area, light green represents shrub, and white represents rock and sand. This is significant because for a certain region, a missile launch could be less likely to

come from a forested area compared to a more open area. Road networks are important because missiles will most likely be driven on roads.

FIGURE 5
ROADS & LAND COVER MAP

Once the parameters are identified, the algorithm encoded in the software will be enabled. This algorithm will produce a map identifying the different possible launch sites most accommodating to the input parameters. Figure 6 depicts this, where the gray areas represent these potential sites.

FIGURE 6
POTENTIAL LAUNCH SITES

Once this map is produced, it can be further filtered to display a specific missile type map as shown below. This is beneficial because map will show the possible launch sites within radius of the identified missile type. So if a commander is concerned about their defended assets, this map would be helpful because it would identify if it would reach the defended asset or not in a Forward Operational Assessment.

FIGURE 7
MISSILE TYPE SPECIFIC MAP WITH LEGEND

Once the map is finalized in ArcGIS, the user has the option of deciding what type of file to save it as for a friendly user interface. These different files include Keyhole Markup Language (KML), HLA, DIS, or COT file types. These different file types have the ability to integrate with other systems, and specialized companies such as Lockheed Martin to provide a common operating picture. Specifically, the Cursor on target or COT, would be the top recommendation for these outputs. Cursor-on-Target (COT) is an Internet Protocol and an XML based machine-to-machine schema that can be read and understood by any system, enabling proprietary and open source systems to communicate with each other [4]. The schema can be used to transmit data from unmanned sensors to collector databases or be displayed on ArcGIS systems to indicate, for example, contamination expansion during a chemical disaster [4]. Additionally, a KML should be used after the map in ArcGIS is produced. KML is an XML-based language provided by Google™ for defining the graphic display of spatial data in applications such as Google Earth™ and Google Maps™ [5]. KML enables these applications to support the open integration of custom data layers from many GIS users [6]. KML data can also be served dynamically on the Web using KML network links. ArcGIS Server can provide dynamic KML content through this mechanism [6]. Ideally, this common operating picture will be available for a Company Commander to see so he or she would be able to aggregate all available information to analyze and make a decision on what to do with potential launch sites.

Looking towards the way ahead, it would be beneficial to incorporate the graphical user interface system Raptor X. Raptor X includes a streamlined terminal interface that allows users to select a desired satellite from an easy-to-navigate, on-screen menu assisting dish alignment [6]. The package also includes a Web-based Graphical User Interface that allows remote monitoring from any standard Web browser [6]. Figure 8 shows a screen shot from Raptor X that illustrates an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle and its track being visualized.

FIGURE 8
RAPTOR X SCREENSHOT

The yellow crosses representing personnel that have been spotted by other sensors. Sensors could be ground radar or cameras that have been able to feed the locations to Raptor X. These yellow crosses could represent likely launch sites predicted by ArcGIS and exported to Raptor X so the battle captain in the Tactical Operation Center can assign a friendly asset to destroy them prior to launch.

CONCLUSION

This model is both an improvement over last year's model as well as a useful product in its own right. Upon completion, this model will be a useful tool for both Lockheed Martin Corporation and the United States Army. Lockheed Martin will integrate this tool into their Integrated Air and Missile Defense Test Bed in order to better simulate missile engagements. The Army will use this tool as a way to prepare to enter a new battlespace and prepare for future engagements.

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